

REALIZATION OF THE CONCEPT "TIME" IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The article dedicated to the concept of time. The linguists' and scientists' as A.V. Westphalian, I. Newton, Leibniz, D.S. Likhacheva, Z.D. Popova, A. M. Peshkovsky, A. A. Shakhmatov, V. V. Vinogradov, A. Kh. Vostokov and others point of views and ideas about the concept of time analyzed. Verbalization of the concept of "time" in English adages and aphorisms also investigated. The question of the connection between language and intellection is one of the main problems of theoretical linguistics. Despite the fact that the exact mechanisms of their interaction have not yet been identified, it is generally recognized that the conceptual and linguistic picture of the world are closely interconnected, which means that the language reflects the experience of its speakers. Inside the linguistic picture of the world, the phraseological, based on paremias, is highlighted as one of the most significant.

KEY WORDS: *Adages, Paremias, Concept, Linguistic Projection, Lexical Units, Syntactic Concepts, Temporality.*

INTRODUCTION

The question of the connection between language and intellection is one of the main problems of theoretical linguistics. Despite the fact that the exact mechanisms of their interaction have not yet been identified, it is generally recognized that the conceptual and linguistic picture of the world are closely interconnected, which means that the language reflects the experience of its speakers. Inside the linguistic picture of the world, the phraseological, based on paremias, is highlighted as one of

the most significant. Adages and aphorisms, as types of paremias, reflect the experience of a nation's social, historical and spiritual meanings and ideas that are important for a given nation. Due to the close connection with the life of the people and events from its history, paremias are often evaluative and have connotations that arise depending on the people's experience. According to A.V. Westphalian: "A positive or negative evaluative element is a defining component of the connotation and is due not only to the centuries-old system of moral culture of each nation, but the political and ideological platform of a particular state at a certain stage of its development" [1, p. one]. All this makes proverbs and sayings a good material for analyzing the verbalization of concepts and complex concepts in a language. Time is an abstract concept and phenomenon underlying both linguistic and scientific pictures of the world. Many scientists and philosophers tried to study this phenomenon in order to answer questions such as: what is the nature of time, its properties, does time exist at all, why does it move in only one direction, etc. As early as in antiquity appeared two opposite points of view. The first was held by Plato; the philosopher understood time as an image of a moving eternity that exists independently of material bodies and processes. Aristotle believed that the existence of time is possible only thanks to consciousness [2]. These two points of view are reflected in physics and natural science: I. Newton argued that time is an independent stream flowing from the past to the future, while Leibniz wrote in his writings that time is a subjective way of perceiving the surrounding reality [2]. In modern physics, since the 20th century, a complex concept of time as a phenomenon dependent on the material conditions of a closed system and having certain metric properties. The passage of time can be slowed down or accelerated depending on the conditions [2]. The complexity of the phenomenon of time and its significant role in the picture of the world has caused the emergence of many of its interpretations in other sciences. These essentially unrelated concepts are based in part on the physical properties of time. So, for example, the course of time and its properties, studied in physics, are reflected in the language of man. Linguistic time is "a linguistic projection of a

complex of existing human knowledge about this phenomenon, from everyday to scientific” [2, p. 2].Linguistic time participates in the transformation of the surrounding reality into a linguistic picture of the world and expresses the connection between language, human activity and objective reality. As we can see, time is a very complex phenomenon, all facets of which, one way or another, are reflected in the language in the form of linguistic time. In order to adequately describe the content side of such complex linguistic signs, the term "concept" is used. This can be traced in the definition of the concept by D.S. Likhacheva: the concept is "the result of the collision of the dictionary meaning of a word with the personal and national experience of a person" [4,p. 3]. Specifically, the concept of "time" is a basic and universal concept, one of the most important components of the conceptual picture of the world.It is important that the phenomenon of time is present in the consciousness and language of the people not only as a way of temporal orientation, but also as a series of “stopped moments” [6, p. 112]. In Russian studies, first of all, aspects and issues of time as a grammatical category were studied. These traditions are laid down in the works of A. M. Peshkovsky, A. A. Shakhmatov, V. V. Vinogradov, A. Kh. Vostokov and others. However, any concept can be verbalized lexically The problem of concept verbalization is considered in detail by Z.D.Popova and I.A.Sternin in "Essays on Cognitive Linguistics" [5]. Linguistic means are necessary only for the expression of the concept, but not for its existence. In addition, only the most significant concepts have linguistic means of expression, most of the concepts exist only in the human mind, their transition to the verbal form is optional [5].There are the following means of verbalizing a concept in a language: ready-made lexical units and stable expressions of the lexicalphraseological system of the language (however, words do not convey the concept in full, they express a set of individual concept features necessary to convey a specific message); free phrases, sentence schemes (or syntactic concepts); as well as texts or collections of texts (for complex, abstract or individual-author’s concepts) [5]. The vocabulary expressing temporality is varied in nature. These are any lexical units associated with the passage of time or a specific

moment in time: minute, year, week, yesterday, Friday. Also, adverbs of time and adverbs of place with the meaning of temporality (eg, long, far). Time can be expressed with the help of lexical units, initially related to space in semantics, and vice versa: “Where did he rent a room? “Ten minutes from my house” or “Do we still have a long drive? “A couple of kilometers.”In addition to the cases described, temporality is verbalized by words associated with certain historical epochs or events: mammoth, Spanish boot, Babylon, Leonardo da Vinci. Since a concept is, first of all, a body of knowledge, experience and ideas, a person who has the necessary information has associations with the necessary period of history. Investigating the verbalization of the concept of "time" in English using the example of proverbs and sayings, we limited ourselves to nouns and prepositions. We analyzed 17 paremias from 4 dictionaries: "The Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs" (5th and 6th editions), bilingual dictionary by M. I. Dubrovin "English and Russian proverbs and sayings in illustrations" and online dictionaries "Cambridge Academic Content Dictionary "and" Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary & Thesaurus ". The lexical unit time is the basis and core of the concept of time in the English language. Other lexical units that verbalize the concept are used to name and measure time intervals: minute, day, week, year, era, tonight, moment, month names - January, February, March, etc., days of the week - Monday, Tuesday , Wednesday, etc., time of day - morning, day, evening, etc. Also these are groups of words used to denote the past, present and future (yesterday, today, tomorrow and past, present, future), space-time prepositions (before, after) and words related to historical periods and eras. The connection with time, its properties, especially metric, can be traced in the definitions of these words. For example, hour is defined as “the twenty-fourth part of the day and night, 60 minutes” and “time of day, moment in time” in the Oxford English Dictionary [11]. In the same place, year is “the time it takes the Earth to complete one revolution around the sun, equal to 365 days, 5 hours, 48 minutes and 46 seconds” [11]. Months in the Cambridge English Dictionary are described as a period of time between the previous and the following month, which has a certain

position in the time measurement system: December - "the twelfth and last month of the year, after November and before January", August - "the eighth month of the year, after July and until September "[9]. There is also a connection with human observations of how time affects the world around: one of the definitions of the noun time is "this process and its influence on people and things" [11]. In the process of analyzing proverbs and sayings with lexical units that verbalize temporality, we have identified the following semantic groups.

1. Paremiyas, which describe the influence of time on a person and the world around him, including the hope that changes for the better will occur. This semantic group is the most numerous, it makes up about half of the entire study material (14 examples out of 27): "Time and tide wait for no man", "Other days, other ways", "Tomorrow is another day", etc. The proverb "Time and tide wait for no man" has the following meaning: natural processes occur without human participation, therefore, if an opportunity is missed, it may not appear again for a long time [3]. This pair reflects, firstly, the fact that time moves, due to an indirect comparison of time with the ebb and flow - natural processes constantly replacing each other. Secondly, it is shown that a person cannot influence the course of time in any way, just as he cannot change the process of ebb and flow. The phrase "Time is a great healer" echoes the ancient idea that time heals. More often it concerns feelings and emotions of a person, rather than his physical condition [12]. In this example, we see a reflection of the observation and experience of man from ancient times. People must have paid attention to the fact that feelings and emotions subside over time, which was subsequently consolidated in the form of this phrase. Similar in semantics and syntax, the pairs "Other times, other manners", "Other times, other customs", "Other days, other ways" are found in different languages [12]. Consequently, the ideas expressed in them can be considered universal, that is, common to people of different cultures. In the first two cases, time is plural. This is due to the fact that this word means a certain historical period, and not time as an abstract concept. In the last example, the noun times is replaced by the word days, which acts as a contextual

synonym and means “a period of the past or present” [11]. The proverb has the following meaning: along with the passage of time, the customs, traditions and rules of society change, as the very way of life of society changes. Knowing that time can affect the world around them and the person himself, people reflected in the saying “Time will tell” the hope that time will put everything in its place, and that later it will be possible to understand whether this or that decision was correct or no [7]. Separately, in the first semantic group, a subgroup of paremias can be distinguished, which reflect a person’s hope for the best: “The darkest hour is that before the dawn” and “Tomorrow is another day”. In the first proverb of the subgroup, the word hour is described by the adjective dark in a superlative degree: on the one hand, it has the metaphorical meaning of a difficult time, and on the other hand, it is a consequence of human observation of nature and the cycles of changing the time of day. The word hour it is used in the meaning of "a short indefinite period of time" [11]. Also, temporality is expressed by the preposition before in the temporal meaning and the noun dawn, which together create a dynamic picture and convey the movement of time. Their combined use also indicates the passage of time (if there is tomorrow, then there is also today and yesterday), which also creates a dynamic picture. Moving time in both examples is a reference to the property of this phenomenon to change the surrounding reality, which allows expressing the main idea of both proverbs - sooner or later things should get better. 2. Paremias about a careful attitude to time, the danger of procrastination and the need to be punctual, otherwise you can miss out on the benefits and present yourself in an unfavorable light.

It is quite obvious that time is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon, which is why its nature has always been controversial for the natural sciences and philosophy. All these contradictory and complex ideas about time have found a significant reflection in the conceptual and linguistic (especially, phraseological) pictures of the world, which was confirmed by the study. As a basic concept, the concept of "time" is widely and variedly represented in the proverbs and sayings of the English language. Folk aphorisms reflect both the physical properties of time and

the results of centuries of observation of a person over him, as well as national traits, as well as the mentality of native speakers. In addition, the temporal concept in proverbs conveys vital information from ancestors to descendants and helps to describe the realities of the surrounding world more simply and clearly.

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